

Kinetics of Substitution of Ethylenediamine from Tris(ethylenediamine)chromium(III) Ion by Dipicolinic Acid

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The mechanistic aspect of the replacement of coordinated water in chromium(III) aquo complexes by an anion or a chelating agent has been controversial. Mechanisms^{1,2} involving two reaction paths, viz. ligand independent path and ligand dependent path, have been suggested independently. As associative mechanism³ involving ion-pair has also been proposed in substitution reactions. Kinetics of substitution of a chelating agent by a multidentate ligand comprises simultaneous breaking and making of bonds and the rates are found to depend upon the nature of entering and leaving ligands and the experimental conditions. The literature survey does not reveal the kinetics of substitution of ethylenediamine from tris(ethylenediamine)chromium(III) chloride by dipicolinic acid. So the present study was carried out to investigate and to elucidate the reaction mechanism of $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ -DPA system.

Results and Discussion

The Fig. 1 represents the spectral changes occurring during the kinetic run recorded periodically (time depending on the rate of reaction) at 338.15 K. The pseudo-first order rate constants (K_{obs}) obtained from the slopes of plots at different initial concentrations of $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ ranging between 0.5×10^{-3} and $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at ionic strength $\mu = 0.25 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 5.0, $[\text{DPA}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, at 338.15 K varied from 2.32×10^{-4} to $2.37 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, are practically constant, confirming the unit order dependence of rate on $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$. The K_{obs} values decreased with increase in ionic strength (maintained by NaNO_3) indicating participa-

tion of ions of opposite charge in the transition state. The value of $Z_A Z_B = 1.08$, which is smaller than the value expected if the reactants were $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ and DPA^{2-} (Table 1). The factor which appears to affect the value of $Z_A Z_B$ may be the possible formation of ion pairs between $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$

Fig. 1. Repetitive scan of the reaction mixture during a typical kinetic run ($[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ + DPA system) at different time intervals: (1) 10, (2) 30, (3) 60, (4) 90, (5) 120 and (6) 180 min; $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+} = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{DPA}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 4.0, $\mu = 0.25 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3), temp = 338.15 K.

and DPA^{2-} ions present in sufficient concentration in the reaction medium. The observed rate constant values in presence of inert electrolytes, i.e. NaNO_3 , KNO_3 , NaCl , KCl , CsCl and NaClO_4 at a constant ionic strength ranged between 2.08 and $2.30 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, are almost constant and show that the reaction is insensitive to the nature of inert electrolytes. K_{obs}

values increase slowly with increase in pH (a linear relationship between $\log K_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log 1/[\text{H}^+]$), but beyond pH 4.5 the increase is rather rapid (data beyond pH 5.0 not shown in Table 1). The protonation tendency of dipicolinate anion being high at lower pH values, the donor capability of the ligand decreases resulting in the decrease in the value of K_{obs} ($\text{p}K_1$ and $\text{p}K_2$ of DPAH_2 are 2.10 and 4.68)⁴. At pH 5.0 and above, DPA mainly exists in dianionic form. The donor capability of DPA increases for

obey Arrhenious temperature dependence. Activation parameters have been evaluated for a gross rate constants k_1 and k_2 using Eyring plots (plots between $-\log kh/KT$ vs $1/T$, Fig. 3.) The activation parameters ΔH_1^* , ΔH_2^* , ΔS_1^* and ΔS_2^* at 313.15 K are 86.41, 96.35 (kJ mol^{-1}), -65.97 and $-10.21 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

Fig. 2 Effect of DPA concentration on rate constant of $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ + DPA system at various temperatures : (A) 318 15, (B) 323 15, (C) 328 15 and (D) 333.15 K, $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+} = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{DPA}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 3.5$

the dipicolinate anion. So the K_{obs} value is higher. Similar observation was obtained by earlier workers² while studying the substitution of aquo ligands from *cis*-diaquo(bis-oxalato)chromium(III) ion by DPA. At a fixed concentration of $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$, the rate constant values at different temperatures increase with increasing concentration of substituting ligand in a linear fashion (Fig. 2). The reaction was found to

TABLE 1-EFFECT ON $[\text{DPA}]$, pH , $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ AND IONIC STRENGTH (μ) ON K_{obs}

Temp = 338 15 K				
$10^2 [\text{DPA}]$ mol dm^{-3}	pH	$10^3 [\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ mol dm^{-3}	μ mol dm^{-3}	$10^4 K_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}
20	5.0	0.5	0.250 (NaNO ₃)	2.32
20	5.0	1.0	0.250	2.33
20	5.0	2.0	0.250	2.30
20	5.0	3.0	0.250	2.30
20	5.0	4.0	0.250	2.37
20	5.0	5.0	0.250	2.50
20	5.0	2.0	0.125	2.64
20	5.0	2.0	0.250	2.30
20	5.0	2.0	0.500	2.09
20	5.0	2.0	1.000	1.95
20	5.0	2.0	2.000	1.66
20	5.0	2.0	0.250 (KNO ₃)	2.34
20	5.0	2.0	0.250 (NaCl)	2.08
20	5.0	2.0	0.250 (KCl)	2.14
20	5.0	2.0	0.250 (CsCl)	2.25
20	5.0	2.0	0.250 (NaClO ₄)	2.30
20	2.5	2.0	0.250	1.44
20	3.0	2.0	0.250	1.65
20	3.5	2.0	0.250	1.79
20	4.0	2.0	0.250	1.92
20	4.5	2.0	0.250	2.05
20	5.0	2.0	0.250	2.30
10	3.5	2.0	0.250	0.96*
15	3.5	2.0	0.250	1.06*
20	3.5	2.0	0.250	1.12*
25	3.5	2.0	0.250	1.20*
30	3.5	2.0	0.250	1.25*
40	3.5	2.0	0.250	1.43*

*Values at 313 15 K

The variation in rate with change in substituting ligand concentration and increase with increasing pH, is in accordance with the following equation expressing K_{obs} as a composite constant

$$\frac{d[\text{Complex-II}]}{dt} = K_{\text{obs}} [\text{Complex-I}]$$

$$K_{\text{obs}} = \left[k_1 + \frac{k_2}{[\text{H}^+]} \text{Ty} \right]$$

where Ty is substituting ligand, k_1 and k_2 are the rate constants, evaluated from the intercept and slope, respectively, of the linear plot between K_{obs} and substituting ligand concentration (Fig. 2). The results suggest that the reaction proceeds through the following steps :

On the basis of the above elementary steps for the substitution of ethylenediamine from tris(ethylenediamine)chromium(III) ion by 2,6-pyridine dicarboxylic acid the following rate equation can be deduced.

The substitution involves the rupture of Cr-N chelate rings, which is taken as the rate-determining step. It is then followed by much more rapid stages leading to the product. Similar assumption was made by earlier workers⁵ while studying the substitution of ethylenediamine from tris(ethylenediamine)-chromium(III) chloride by EDTA. The overall rate may be expressed as

$$\text{Rate} = \left[k_1 + \frac{k''}{[\text{H}^+]} \text{Ty} \right] [\text{Complex-I}] \quad (5)$$

It is also assumed that the equilibrium constants K_1 and K_2 for the reactions (2) and (3) are small enough so that all the unreacted complex is present essentially as $[\text{Cr(en)}_3]^{3+}$. Equation (5) may be modified to

$$\text{Rate} = \left[k_1 + \frac{k_2}{[\text{H}^+]} \text{Ty} \right] \text{Tc} \quad (6)$$

where $\text{Tc} = [\text{Complex-I}]$ and $k_2 = k''K_{a1}K_{a2}K_1K_2$, K_{a1} and K_{a2} being dissociation constants of DPAH_2 .

Fig. 3. Eyring plot for $[\text{Cr(en)}_3]^{3+} + \text{DPA}$ system (effect of temperature).

The negative value of entropy change may be due to the formation of ion-pairs and transition species with a lower charge formed from the oppositely charged reactants. Thus it is expected to increase the structure-breaking effect of the ion-pair on the solvent due to increase in the size of the transition species. The solvent is thus made less ordered around the transition complex species and this increase in the positive effect brings down the negative entropy change. The ion-pair mechanism is further confirmed from the pH effect on reaction rate. The reaction rate is slow at low pH values due to slow protonation of carboxylate ion of the ligand. The increase in rate constant values beyond pH 4.5, is due to increased donor capability of dipicolinate anion. This phenomenon indicates that dipicolinate anion takes part in the rate-determining steps.

Experimental

All reagents used were of highest available grade. Chromic chloride ($\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (AnalaR) was dried in a hot air-oven (383–393 K) before use.

Tris(ethylenediamine)chromium(III) chloride (Complex-I) was prepared by the reported method⁶. The purity of Complex-I was checked by elemental analysis and ir spectra. Dipicolinic acid (Aldrich) solutions of desired concentrations were prepared in glass-distilled water.

Kinetic experiments were carried out spectrophotometrically using a CE599 (J) (CECIL Instruments Ltd.) spectrophotometer.

Due to high solubility of the product (complex-II) it could not be isolated in pure crystalline form. However, its formation in solution was indicated by kinetic run recorded periodically, thermostated at 338.15 K for 24 h by following the absorbance of reaction mixture. The absorbance decreased at 460 nm for $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ and increased at 552 nm for complex-II. Composition of complex-II in solution (1 : 3) was confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation. pH of the reaction medium was adjusted by NaOH/HNO₃ using a Systronic pH meter. Ionic strength was adjusted by NaNO₃. The course of reaction was followed measuring absorbances at 552 nm where substantial differences existed in the molar extinction coefficients of Complex-I (ϵ_M , 12.5) and complex-II (Product) (ϵ_M 195).

The concentration of the substituting ligand, dipicolinic acid, was always maintained high so that

pseudo-first order rate law could be applied. The pseudo-first order rate constant (K_{obs}) was determined graphically by plotting $\log (A_{\alpha}-A_0)/(A_{\alpha}-A_t)$ vs time, where A_0 , A_t and A_{α} are respectively, the initial optical density values, after time t and after completion of the reaction.

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